

Conference Abstract

Contributions to the terrestrial isopods (Crustacea, Isopoda, Oniscidea) from Brazilian caves

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Abstract

Terrestrial isopods (Oniscidea) comprise more than 3,700 species distributed in almost all types of the terrestrial habitats, including caves. About 300 troglobiotic species are known, mostly in the northern hemisphere. In South America, Brazil has the highest number of recorded caves, approximately 15,000 (7% of the total estimated, ca. 100,000). Currently, 37 species of terrestrial isopods are known from Brazilian caves, 15 of which are considered troglobiotic. A large collection of terrestrial isopods from caves of the Brazilian states of Pará, Sergipe, Bahia, Minas Gerais, Goiás, São Paulo, Mato Grosso, Mato Grosso do Sul, and Paraná has been examined. Fifty-three species are recognized in the families Styloniscidae (3 genera, 4 species), Rhyscotidae (1 genus, 1 species), Philosciidae (6 genera, 11 species), Scleropactidae (3 genera, 4 species), Platyarthridae (2 genera, 14 species), Dubioniscidae (2 genera, 12 species), Armadillidae (4 genera, 5 species), Porcellionidae (1 genus, 1 species), and Armadillidiidae (1 genus, 1 species). Eight species can be considered troglobiotic in the genera *Xangoniscus* (2 spp.) (Styloniscidae), *Alboscia* (1 spp.), *Atlantoscia* (1 spp.) and *Benthana* (1 spp.) (Philosciidae), *Amazoniscus* (1 spp.) and *Microsphaeroniscus* (1 spp.) (Scleropactidae), and one new genus with two new species of Platyarthridae. A second species of the genus *Pectenoniscus* (Styloniscidae), a new genus of a spiny Armadillidae with two new species

are described, the poorly known *Venezillo congener* is re-described, and many species have their recorded distributions extended. The total number of cave-dwelling species in Brazil is still far to be complete. It is very important to increase research on cave biodiversity which is threatened by anthropic actions (e.g., monocultures and mining), and to define conservation strategies according to the current legislation.

Keywords

terrestrial isopods, biodiversity, cave environment, Neotropical region

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All authors contributed equally to the development of the work.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.